

ON THE NEED TO PROVIDE MEDICAL CARE, NOT FIGHT DRUG ADDICTS

Abdurazakov Abduvosit Abdulkhaevich

Deputy Head of the Main Department of Internal Affairs
of Tashkent City - Head of the Investigation Department, colonel

E-mail: vosit_8119@mail.ru

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.12698557>

Abstract: The article, along with the fight against drug addiction, examines the need to provide medical care to those suffering from this disease. Based on analytical materials from the UN and national countries, medical problems related to drug addiction among adults, youth and minors are analyzed. Opinions on recent changes in national legislation on these issues were discussed.

Keywords: drug addiction, youth, disease, medical rehabilitation, intoxication, addiction.

Аннотация: Мақолада гиёҳвандлик билан курашиш билан бир қаторда, дардга чалинганларга тиббий ёрдам бериш зарурати кўриб чиқилади. БМТ ва миллий таҳлилий материаллар асосида катталар, ёшлар ва вояга етмаганларнинг гиёҳвандлик ларидига чалинишига оид тиббий муаммолар таҳлил қилинади. Ушбу масалалар бўйича миллий қонунчиликдаги сўнгги ўзгаришлар ҳақида фикр сурилади.

Калит сўзлар: гиёҳвандлик, ёшлар, касаллик, тиббий соғломлаштириш, заҳарвандлик, қарамлик.

Гиёҳвандлик воситалари, уларнинг аналоглари ва психотроп моддалар билан қонунга хилоф равишда муомала қилишга оид жиноятлар аҳоли соғлиғига, жамиятнинг иқтисодий ва маънавий негизига жиддий таҳдид солади, оилавий муносабатларга салбий таъсир кўрсатади, бошқа ижтимоий муаммолар келтириб чиқаради.

Гиёҳвандлик – наркотик моддаларга ўрганиб қолиш, аниқроғи, табиий ёки заҳарли синтетик моддаларни (айрим дори моддалари) вақтинча ёки сурункасига истеъмол қилиш натижасида келиб чиқадиган касаллик. Гиёҳвандлик танада ва руҳиятда жиддий ўзгариш юз беришига сабаб бўлади ва гиёҳвандни таназзулга олиб боради. Бу эса ўз навбатида, нафақат гиёҳвандга, балки бутун жамиятга кўплаб зарар етказди.

People who are weak-willed, can't control themselves, are interested in experimenting with sharp senses, mentally weak and extremely selfish people are addicted to drugs. Defects and shortcomings in the education of young people, imitation and envy of adults who use drugs, unpleasant family

conditions (parents are alcoholics or drug addicts) and easy access to drugs are also causes of drug addiction.

The harms of drug addiction to society are many. A person who suffers from it has no interest in himself first, then in his family, profession or studies. It is especially sad that the young generation, which is the main force of production and development, is the first victim of drug addiction. In particular, according to the latest World Drug Report published by the United Nations Office on Drugs and Crime (UNODC), in 2020, approximately 270 million people around the world used drugs (cannabis, opium), which is 5.2% of the world's population. [1].

The same report on drug use trends states, "In 2020, cannabis is the most widely used psychoactive substance in the world, with an estimated 209 million people using it worldwide. However, opioids continue to pose the greatest threat to human health." Over the past decade, opioid overdose deaths account for two-thirds of all drug-related deaths, with an increase of 92 percent among men compared to 63 percent among women.[1]

The negative consequences of this problem are not only for the individual or society, but also for the development of the whole country, and it can cause the political system and legislation to fail.

As stated in the UN Convention against Illicit Traffic in Narcotic Drugs and Psychotropic Substances, "in many regions of the world, children appear as illegal consumers of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances and use these drugs in the organization of their illegal production and trafficking, which is serious in itself. is becoming a danger...".[2]

According to the legislation, those guilty of illegal preparation, acquisition, storage, transportation or sending of small amounts of narcotic drugs, their analogues without the intention of transferring psychotropic substances are subject to administrative liability in all cases. If these actions are carried out for the purpose of transfer, the act is qualified by part 1 of Article 273 of the Civil Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan.

Therefore, the injection (syringe) of narcotic drugs, their analogs and psychotropic substances by one person to another, if this drug or substance belongs to the consumer himself and the injection was made at his request, is not considered illegal transfer.

In cases related to crimes related to the illegal handling of narcotic drugs, their analogues, and psychotropic substances, a narcological examination should be conducted in necessary cases to determine whether the culprit is addicted to

drugs or intoxication and to decide whether to send him to compulsory treatment, if in the conclusion of the narcological examination, the person is forced if it is concluded that he needs treatment, in accordance with Article 96 of the Criminal Code of the Republic of Uzbekistan, compulsory treatment for drug addiction or intoxication is prescribed for a person, in which compulsory treatment can be assigned not only to prisoners who have been deprived of their freedom, but also to prisoners who have been sentenced to a sentence that is not related to the deprivation of their freedom.

The spread of drug addiction among young people is more dangerous than the spread among adults. Addiction of one of the youth directly causes great damage to the family to which he belongs, which can be seen mainly in the following:

- • violation of marital relations;
- • increase of diseases;
- • impoverishment;
- • birth of a disabled child;
- • failure of children's upbringing;
- • teach this vice to their children;
- • loss of human qualities and degradation;
- • many cases of family breakdown and orphaning of children.

Allah Almighty has given countless blessings to man, and the servant should use the blessings given to him in a way that is useful for the life of this world and the hereafter. He says in the Holy Qur'an: "Do not forget your destiny with what Allah has given you and your destiny in this world. Give charity (to people) as God has given you charity! Don't want to mess up on the ground. Because God does not love the corrupters" (Surah Al-Qasas, verse 77) or in another place: "Also eat and drink, (but) do not waste! Because he does not love the spendthrift." (Surah A'raf, verse 31)

In this place, the deputy chairman of the republican social and information center Sh. According to Kasimova, the issue of "drug stores" is brought up in each of our events organized by the Center. "What will happen if young people take 2-3 types of psychotropic drugs together?" questions arise. From this it can be said that there are cases of doing this among young people.

We implemented a project among girls from the socially vulnerable group aged 14-18 in Tashkent. Among girls with severe behavior, 4 drug or psychotropic substance users were identified. When we asked 17-18-year-old girls about when they started this business, they answered that they were 14-15

years old. They said that at first they took 1 or 2 psychoactive pills a day, but now they are taking 40 a day. There are no family conditions for treatment. Unfortunately, even at the state level, there is no system to help such girls" [4].

But now, the situation in this matter will change. On May 6 of this year, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan signed the decree No. PF-73 [5] "On strategic measures to eliminate the negative impact of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances on the public health and the gene pool of our country by putting an end to the illegal circulation of narcotic drugs and psychotropic substances in the Republic of Uzbekistan". According to the decree, the national strategy for combating drug addiction and drug crimes for 2024-2028 was adopted.

The following measures are planned within this National Strategy:

- A republican fund will be established for the development of the field of combating drug addiction.
- For early detection of drug use among schoolchildren, the practice of scheduled psychologist and, if necessary, narcologist consultations is introduced.
- An electronic platform "Toward a Healthy Life" will be created for women and young people in difficult social situations.
- Latent addicts are identified by creating a social mobile application that provides real-time counseling to drug abusers.
- The practice of using VR (Virtual Reality) technology will be established in the treatment of drug addicts.
- In order to bring the narcology service closer to the population, a Call-center will be launched, which will provide confidential advice.

In conclusion, in addition to strengthening the medical system, first of all, it is necessary to further improve the efficiency of work on improving the legal knowledge of the population about the drug epidemic, the legal culture in general, the introduction of modern methods of legal education of citizens in harmony with social and political changes, as well as the population, especially, it is necessary to form strong legal immunity to protect young people from harmful information.

References:

1. https://www.unodc.org/res/wdr2022/MS/WDR22_Booklet_1_russian.pdf
2. Международные Конвенции по защите прав человека и борьбе с преступностью: (Сб. междунар. документов) /Сост. Ю.С. Пулатов. – Т.: Шарк, 1995. - С. 302.
3. Гиёҳванд моддалар ҳам стратегик қуролдир // <http://old.muslim.uz/index.php/maqolalar/item/4275>

4. Жамоатчилик мулоқоти: наркотик ва психотроп моддаларнинг ноқонуний айланмаси муаммолари // <https://uzpharmagency.uz/uz/news/uzbekistonda-dorihona-narkomanijasini-andaj-ilib-juotish-mumkin>
5. Ўзбекистон Республикаси Президентининг 2024 йил 6 майдаги ПФ-73-сон Фармони // Қонунчилик маълумотлари миллий базаси, 07.05.2024 й., 06/24/73/0327-сон

